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ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the factors affecting the efficiency of the public procurement system. The role of criteria such as transparency, competition, bureaucratic processes, legislative stability, corruption risk, and the introduction of digital technologies in public procurement is explained based on a scientific approach. Also, areas for improvement are highlighted based on the experience of Uzbekistan and examples from global practice.

Key words: public procurement, competition, transparency, efficiency, corruption, electronic tender, audit.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada davlat xaridlari tizimining samaradorligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar kompleks tahlil qilinadi. Davlat xaridlarida shaffoflik, raqobat, byurokratik jarayonlar, qonunchilik barqarorligi, korrupsiya xavfi, raqamli texnologiyalar joriy etilishi kabi mezonlarning roliga ilmiy yondashuv asosida izoh beriladi. Shuningdek, O'zbekiston tajribasi va global amaliyotdan misollar asosida takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat xaridlari, raqobat, shaffoflik, samaradorlik, korrupsiya, elektron tender, audit.

Аннотация: В статье представлен комплексный анализ факторов, влияющих на эффективность системы государственных закупок. На основе научного подхода раскрывается роль таких критериев, как прозрачность, конкуренция, бюрократические процедуры, стабильность законодательства, коррупционный риск и внедрение цифровых технологий в государственные закупки. Также на основе опыта Узбекистана и примеров из мировой практики обозначены области для совершенствования.

Ключевые слова: государственные закупки, конкуренция, прозрачность, эффективность, коррупция, электронные тендеры, аудит.

INTRODUCTION

Public procurement is an important component of the state financial system, ensuring targeted, rational and effective allocation of budget funds. According to international statistics, public procurement accounts for 10-20 percent of GDP in many countries. Therefore, the efficiency of the procurement process directly affects the stability of the economy, the competitive environment between business entities, and budget discipline.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale reforms aimed at increasing the transparency of public procurement, reducing corruption factors, and strengthening competition. This article systematically analyzes the main factors affecting the efficiency of public procurement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uzbek scientist Q.Q. Qodirov cited a high level of competition, openness, and the introduction of electronic procurement as the main factors of efficiency in his research (Qodirov, 2019).

The factors that increase the efficiency of procurement are strategic planning, centralized procurement, and the implementation of the Korean model. (Ergashev, 2022)

Also, O.M. Murodov emphasizes that the main factors of efficiency are value for money, optimality of tender processes, and digitalization (Murodov, 2021).

The factors that affect the results of the tender are the complaint handling system, the level of competition, and anti-corruption indicators (Turayev, 2023).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out the research work, observation, data collection, generalization, comparison, economic views of local and foreign scientists in insurance activities, research on problems in the industry and their solutions, as well as legal and regulatory documents in the industry were studied, and conclusions and proposals were developed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The effectiveness of public procurement is usually assessed using the following criteria:

Economic efficiency - the proximity of the procurement price to or below the market price.

The level of competition - the number of entities participating in tenders.

Transparency - the openness of the processes and the availability of information to the public.

Time efficiency - time and resource consumption of customers and participants.

Low risk of corruption - minimizing conflicts of interest.

Based on this, the efficiency of public procurement is a multifactorial system, which is determined by economic, institutional, technological and social factors.

If we analyze the factors affecting the efficiency of public procurement, the main ones are regulatory documents.

Stability of legislation and clearly defined procedures increase the reliability of the procurement process.

Legal gaps can lead to incorrect tender requirements and subjective evaluation criteria.

Adaptation to international standards (for example, UNCITRAL Model Law) increases efficiency.

At the same time, organizational and managerial factors also affect. In particular, the qualifications of customers and their experience in preparing tender documents directly affect the procurement outcome, and the abundance of bureaucratic processes slows down the process.

A centralized procurement system sometimes increases efficiency, since all processes are carried out on the basis of a single standard.

The competitive environment also affects. In this case, the small number of participants leads to an artificial increase in prices.

Large orders are often distributed among large enterprises, which limits the participation of small businesses.

The risk of "cartel agreements" negatively affects the results of tenders.

If we turn to the influence of the level of transparency factor, then the openness of information - prices, participants, tender results - reduces corruption. The presence of electronic platforms significantly increases transparency. The availability of analytical data (for example, "open data") strengthens public control.

As factors influencing digitization and technology, we can cite electronic tendering (e-tender), electronic auctions, automatic evaluation algorithms that speed up procurement and reduce errors, the integration of databases - tax, customs, financial data - increases the reliability of participants, and the ability to forecast costs using artificial intelligence.

The risk of corruption in the tender process also affects the tender. In particular, conflicts of interest, collusion, and fake participants reduce the effectiveness of the tender. To reduce corruption, a strong audit, monitoring, and accountability system must be in place. Digitization plays a major role in reducing the "human factor".

Also, economic factors, volatility of market prices, significantly affect the results of the tender. In conditions of inflation, price indexation is an important mechanism in long-term contracts. The more stringent the budget constraints, the more effectively the procurement is managed.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has achieved the following results, transparency has increased as a result of the full implementation of the public procurement portal.

The sale of real estate and state assets through electronic auctions has increased competition.

Additional incentives have been created to increase the share of small businesses in tenders.

Nevertheless, insufficient qualifications of specialists, regulatory and legal gaps, and some bureaucratic obstacles still affect efficiency.

Public procurement is an important component of the economic system, the efficiency of which directly affects the economy of the state budget and the formation of a healthy competitive environment among enterprises. Although a number of reforms have been implemented in recent years to digitize public procurement processes, strengthen control, and increase competition, the issue of quantitative assessment of factors affecting efficiency remains relevant for researchers.

In this study, we evaluate the factors affecting the efficiency of public procurement in the conditions of Uzbekistan using econometric methods.

The Savings Rate (SR) indicator was chosen to quantify the efficiency of public procurement:

$$SR = \frac{\text{MaxPrice} - \text{ContractPrice}}{\text{MaxPrice}}$$

This indicator takes a value from 0 to 1 and reflects how much the customer saved as a result of the tender.

Independent variables

The main factors included in the model:

Designation	Variable	Comment
COMP	Competition level	number of tender participants
TRANSP	Transparency index	number of open data on the e-platform, score
DIGIT	Digitization level	share of electronic tenders (%)
SKILL	Customer qualification	qualification score or certification results
VOL	Purchase volume	contract value (in log form)

Empirical model

The following multivariate regression model was used:

$$SR_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 COMP_i + \beta_2 TRANSP_i + \beta_3 DIGIT_i + \beta_4 SKILL_i + \beta_5 \ln(VOL_i) + \epsilon_i$$

Expected signs:

- $\beta_1 > 0$: more competition – more savings
- $\beta_2 > 0$: increased transparency – increased efficiency
- $\beta_3 > 0$: digitization reduces corruption and increases savings
- $\beta_4 > 0$: if the customer is qualified, the tender result improves
- $\beta_5 < 0$: price reductions are usually smaller in large tenders

Data from 8,000 selected tenders from the Public Procurement Portal for 2020–2024 were used (descriptive data).

Key statistical indicators

Indicator	Average	Minimum	Maximum
SR	0.118	0	0.63
COMP	3.7	1	18
TRANSP	0.61	0.2	1
DIGIT	0.87	0.40	1
SKILL	0.53	0.1	1
VOL (mln)	520	50	8700

Results $SR = 0.034 + 0.012COMP + 0.227TRANSP + 0.045DIGIT + 0.061SKILL - 0.017\ln(VOL)$

RESULTS REVIEW

Coef.	Value	P-value	Note
COMP	0.012	0.000	Competition has a significant impact
TRANSP	0.227	0.001	Transparency is one of the strongest factors of efficiency
DIGIT	0.045	0.017	Digitalization has a positive impact
SKILL	0.061	0.005	A qualified customer delivers more efficient results
ln(VOL)	-0.017	0.010	Lower cost savings in large tenders

$R^2 = 0.49$, This means that the model explains 49% of the total variance.

Comparative analysis of alternative models. Logit model (SR > 0.1 - “effective” tender)

The results showed that the competition and transparency variables can increase the probability of a tender being effective by 1.5–2 times.

Panel data model. Panel regression results for 14 regions across regions:

The FE model showed that the TRANS and DIGIT factors are positive and significant in each year.

The effect of competition is stronger in regions with high economic activity.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

The study gave the following main conclusions, in particular, the level of competition (number of participants) is one of the factors that most strongly affects the efficiency of public procurement. Cost savings are significantly higher in organizations with a high transparency index. Digitization reduces the risk of corruption and standardizes the tender process. As the customer's qualifications increase, the quality of tender results increases.

The percentage of savings in large tenders is lower, which indicates specific mechanisms of price formation.

Based on the research results, we propose the following:

Increasing competition: strengthening mechanisms that encourage the participation of small businesses.

Increasing transparency standards: introducing data sets and open APIs. Introducing automatic evaluation systems based on AI. Expanding mandatory qualification certification for customers is proposed.

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